

Dipole Moments of some Aryl Methyl and Diaryl Sulphoxides

V. BALIAH* and A. EKAMBARAM

Department of Chemistry, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar-608 002

Manuscript received 27 December 1990, accepted 8 May 1991

Dipole moments of twenty four sulphoxides have been determined. The angle which the moment of SOCH_3 group makes with its axis of rotation is calculated. From this angle and the group moments, the dipole moments of a number of sulphoxides are calculated and compared with the observed moments with a view to knowing the polar and steric effects of the substituents. For sulphoxides with no *ortho*-substitution the calculated moments are in good agreement with the experimental values. Mono-*ortho*-substitution by CH_3 or Cl prevents free rotation of the $-\text{SOCH}_3$ group, directing its orientation away from the substituent. For other sulphoxides the probable conformation of the groups present in the molecule is indicated.

THE scanty dipole moment data¹ available on sulphoxides and the interesting nature of the sulphanyl group in respect of its polarity prompted us to determine experimentally the dipole moments of a number of sulphoxides. The sulphoxide group can function either as electron-acceptor or as electron-donor. The dipole moment data¹, ^{19}F nmr spectra² and pK_a values³ indicate that SOCH_3 is an electron-withdrawing group by *d*-orbital acceptance. Cutress *et al.*⁴ found from a study of ir intensities of methyl phenyl sulphoxides that SOCH_3 is a net electron-donor. Buchanan *et al.*⁵ found the effect of polar substituents on the CH_3SO carbon chemical shifts to be negligible. The ability of the methylsulphinyl group to conjugate strongly with both nitro and acetamido groups in the photoexcited state has been shown⁶ from the uv spectra.

Though powerful *para* electron-withdrawing groups can make the methylsulphinyl group an electron-donor and powerful *para* electron-donating groups an electron-acceptor in the excited state, it is of interest⁷ to know whether the group behaves similarly in the ground state of aryl methyl sulphoxides. It is also of interest to know from dipole moments the steric influence of *ortho*-substituent or substituents in aryl methyl sulphoxides and the conformation of the methylsulphinyl group in such *ortho*-substituted sulphoxides.

Experimental

Dielectric constant of the benzene solution was measured at 30° as described earlier⁷. Density was measured with a 10 ml pycnometer. The dielectric constant and density of at least four solutions of graded concentrations were determined for each compound. From the measured dielectric

constant (ϵ_{12}) and density (d_{12}) of each concentration, the constants α and β were calculated from the following equations,

$$\epsilon_{12} = \epsilon_1 (1 + \alpha w_2)$$

$$d_{12} = d_1 (1 + \beta w_2)$$

where ϵ_1 and d_1 are the dielectric constant and density of the solvent benzene at 30° , w_2 is the weight fraction of the solute; ϵ_1 and d_1 were taken as 2.2628 and 0.8688 respectively. The molar polarisation at infinite dilution (∞P_2) was calculated from the equation⁸,

$$\infty P_2 = \frac{M_2}{d_1} \left[\frac{(\epsilon_1 - 1)(1 - \beta)}{(\epsilon_1 + 2)} + \frac{3 \alpha \epsilon_1}{(\epsilon_1 + 2)^2} \right]$$

where, M_2 is the molecular weight of the solute. The dipole moment (μ) was calculated using equation,

$$\mu = 0.01281 \left[(\infty P_2 - R_D) T \right]^{1/2}$$

where, R_D is the molar refraction of the solute and T the temperature (K). In the case of liquids the molar refraction was calculated from the density and refractive index measurements (Table 1). In the case of solids R_D was estimated from bond refractions⁹. S—O bond refraction was taken¹⁰ as 0.6.

The sulphoxides were obtained from the corresponding sulphides, for most of which references were given in an earlier paper¹¹. The other sulphoxides were prepared according to the general method given below.

The appropriate hydrocarbon or its derivatives in chloroform solution was treated with distilled chlorosulphonic acid¹² and the resulting sulphonyl chloride was reduced to thiophenol with zinc dust and dilute sulphuric acid. The thiophenol so obtained was methylated using dimethyl sulphate and

* Present address : 79, 3rd Cross Road, Venkatanagar, Pondicherry-605 011.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF ARYL METHYL SULPHOXIDES

Sl. no.	Aryl	B.p. °C/mm (M.p. °C)	n_D^{20}	d_4^{20}
1.	Phenyl ^a	118—20/5	1.5755	1.153
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	159—61/20	1.5686	1.124
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl ^b	114—15/0.8	1.5565	1.118
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl ^b	138—40/12	1.5604	1.111
5.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl ^b	126—27/12	1.5472	1.261
6.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	138—40/8	1.5809	1.294
7.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl ^b	158—60/6	1.5870	1.282
8.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl ^b	136—37/8	1.5772	1.299
9.	<i>p</i> -Ethylphenyl	148—49/12	1.5589	1.096
10.	<i>p</i> - <i>i</i> -Propylphenyl	132—33/9	1.5502	1.062
11.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl ^b	134—35/0.75	1.5772	1.192
12.	4-Methoxy-3-methylphenyl	136—37/2	1.5718	1.167
13.	2,6-Dimethylphenyl	140—41/3.5	1.5707	1.118
14.	4-Methoxy-2,5-dimethylphenyl	(74—75)		
15.	<i>p</i> -Acetylphenyl	(105—06)		
16.	4-Methoxy-2,6-dimethylphenyl	164—66/1.2	1.5740	1.140
17.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl ^c	(110—11)		
18.	4-Nitrophenyl ^b	(147—48)		
19.	2-Methyl-4-nitrophenyl	(122—23)		
20.	2,6-Dimethyl-4-nitrophenyl ^d	(165—66)		

*Method of preparation : Compds. sl. nos. 1—12, method A ; 13—15, method B ; 16—20, method C ; Compounds sl. nos. 6, 9, 10, 12—16 and 19 gave satisfactory analyses for C and H. ^aRef. 18. ^bRef. 4. ^cRef. 1^x. ^dRef. 6.

aqueous sodium hydroxide. The methyl sulphide was repeatedly washed with dilute alkali and water, dried and distilled : Methyl *p*-*i*-propylphenyl sulphide, m.p. 243—45° (Found : C, 72.32 ; H, 8.61. C₁₀H₁₄S calcd. for : C, 72.26 ; H, 8.49%) ; 4-Methoxy-3-methylphenyl methyl sulphide, m.p. 258—59° (Found : C, 64.34 ; H, 7.23. C₉H₁₂OS calcd. for : C, 64.22 ; H, 7.19%).

The oxidation of sulphides to sulfoxides was effected by hydrogen peroxide (method A) or chromic anhydride (method B) or nitric acid (method C). A typical preparation according to each of these methods is given below.

Methyl *m*-tolyl sulphoxide : To a solution of the sulphide (19 g) in pure acetone (100 ml), hydrogen peroxide (30% ; 30 ml) was slowly added below 25°. After 24 h, the excess of H₂O₂ was decomposed with manganese dioxide (0.5 g), keeping the product in contact with MnO₂ for 24 h. The acetone solution was then filtered, the solvent removed and the residue extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the solvent removed, and the oil distilled (4.5 g).

Methyl 2,6-dimethylphenyl sulphoxide : The sulphide (5 g) in acetic acid (35 ml) was treated with chromic anhydride (2.5 g) dissolved in minimum amount of water. During addition, the solution was cooled in ice. The mixture was

then heated on a water-bath (60—70°) for 30 min and poured into cold water (250 ml). The solution was neutralised with a saturated solution of Na₂CO₃ and extracted with chloroform (2×50 ml). The chloroform extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, the solvent removed under reduced pressure and the residue fractionated. The fraction boiling at 140—42°/5 mm was collected and redistilled.

***p*-Acetylphenyl methyl sulphoxide :** Fuming nitric acid (30 ml) was cooled in ice-salt mixture and the sulphide (4.2 g) was added gradually so that each lot dissolved well before the next one was added. The reaction mixture was allowed to reach the room temperature and then poured into an ice-cold solution of Na₂CO₃ to neutralise the acid. Any sulphoxide that separated out at this stage was isolated. The alkaline solution was extracted with chloroform. After removal of the solvent, the sulphoxide was crystallised from benzene-ligroin. The yield was nearly quantitative.

Relevant details regarding the aryl methyl sulphoxides prepared are given in Table 1.

Diphenyl sulphoxide, m.p. 70.5—71° (lit.¹³ 71°), was prepared by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of benzene with thionyl chloride. Phenyl *p*-tolyl sulphoxide, m.p. 70—71° (lit.¹⁴ 72°), *p*-nitrodiphenyl sulphoxide, m.p. 109—110° (lit.¹⁵ 107—107.5°), *p*-methoxydiphenyl sulphoxide, m.p. 67—68° (lit.¹⁶ 68°) and di(*p*-methoxyphenyl) sulphoxide, m.p. 95—96° (lit.¹⁷ 95.8°) were prepared by method C.

Results and Discussion

Information on polar and steric effects as well as substituent interactions in aryl methyl sulphoxides can be obtained by calculating their dipole moments from group moments by vector addition and comparing them with the experimentally determined values. The calculation requires a knowledge of the moment of SOCH₃ group and the direction in which the moment acts with reference to the axes of rotation of the group. The angle of the group moment was obtained using the equation²⁰,

$$\mu^2 = \mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2 + 2\mu_1\mu_2 \cos \theta \cos \alpha \cos \beta$$

In a compound like 1, μ is the dipole moment of the molecule, μ_1 the moment of group X, μ_2

1

the moment of SOCH₃, θ the angle between the axes of rotation of the groups, and α and β are the angles which the moments of the groups make with their respective axes of rotation (which are assumed to be directed towards the groups).

Using the above equation and the dipole moments of chlorobenzene (1.57D)¹¹, methyl phenyl sulphoxide (3.94D) and methyl *p*-chlorophenyl sulphoxide (3.35D), the angle which the moment of SOCH₃ makes with its axis of rotation was found to be 57° (the group moments of Cl and SOCH₃ were assumed to be the same as those of chlorobenzene and methyl phenyl sulphoxide, respectively). When the angle was calculated from the dipole moment of methyl *m*-chlorophenyl sulphoxide and the group moments of Cl and SOCH₃, it was found to be 58°. A similar calculation using moments of methyl *p*-fluorophenyl sulphoxide (3.34D), fluorobenzene (1.43D)¹¹ and methyl phenyl sulphoxide (3.94D) gave a value of 55°. The average of these values 57°, i.e. (57+58+55)/3, was taken as the dipole angle of the SOCH₃ group.

An attempt was made to determine the dipole moment of 1,4-dimethylsulphinylbenzene with a view to calculating the above angle from its moment also. But the compound was found to be insoluble in benzene, dioxane, carbon tetrachloride and carbon disulphide. Hence its dipole moment could not be determined.

The dipole moments of a number of aryl methyl sulphoxides were calculated from group moments and their dipole angles. The moment of the CH₃ group was taken as that of toluene (0.34D)^{21,22}, the moments of Et and *i*-Pr groups as those²² of ethylbenzene (0.35D) and *i*-propylbenzene (0.38D) respectively, and the moments of F, I, OCH₃, NO₂ groups as those¹¹ of fluorobenzene (1.43D), iodobenzene (1.36D), anisole (1.25D)

and nitrobenzene (3.95D) respectively. The dipole angle of the CH₃O group was taken¹¹ as 105°. For many sulphoxides the agreement between the observed moments and the moments, calculated for free rotation of groups, is very good (Table 2). There are, however, some sulphoxides whose observed dipole moments differ appreciably from the calculated moments for free rotation of groups. Of the monosubstituted sulphoxides, the *o*-methyl and *o*-chloro compounds show that there is no free rotation of SOCH₃ in their molecules, (*o*-CH₃: $\mu_{f,r}=3.86D$, $\mu_{obs}=4.11D$; *o*-Cl: $\mu_{f,r}=4.62D$, $\mu_{obs}=3.45D$). The moments (*o*-CH₃, 4.11D; *o*-Cl, 3.52D) calculated for the orientation of SOCH₃ away from the *ortho*-substituent (2a and 2b) agree with the observed values. For 2a the agreement is excellent and for 2b it is satisfactory.

It may be seen that the observed and calculated moments of methyl *p*-methoxyphenyl sulphoxide (sl. no. 13 of Table 2) agree very well, indicating absence of conjugative interaction of the methoxy and sulphinyl groups in the ground state of the molecule. In contrast to sulphinyl group, the

TABLE 2—POLARISATION DATA AND DIPOLE MOMENTS OF ARYL METHYL AND DIARYL SULPHOXIDES

Sl. no.	Aryl	α	β	σP_2 (ml)	R_D (ml)	$\mu(D)^*$	
						Obs.	Calcd.**
1.	Phenyl	5.28	0.260	352.3	48.2	3.94	—
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	5.19	0.251	384.2	45.1	4.11	4.11
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	4.98	0.245	370.4	44.6	4.02	4.05
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	5.35	0.240	395.0	45.2	4.17	4.14
5.	2,6-Dimethylphenyl	4.14	0.244	330.5	47.8	3.75	3.76
6.	<i>p</i> -Ethylphenyl	4.91	0.215	399.4	49.6	4.17	4.14
7.	<i>p</i> - <i>i</i> -Propylphenyl	4.60	0.191	409.3	54.7	4.20	4.16
8.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	3.35	0.323	263.6	39.8	3.34	—
9.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	3.28	0.353	281.1	45.0	3.45	3.52
10.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	4.04	0.359	341.1	45.8	3.83	—
11.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	3.11	0.353	271.5	45.6	3.35	—
12.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	2.10	0.543	281.1	52.6	3.37	3.40
13.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	5.03	0.294	419.1	47.3	4.30	4.30
14.	4-Methoxy-3-methylphenyl	4.91	0.287	432.9	52.0	4.35	4.31
15.	4-Methoxy 2,5-dimethylphenyl	6.23	0.266	579.0	55.4	5.10	5.14
16.	4-Methoxy-2,6-dimethylphenyl	4.13	0.275	400.4	55.4	4.14	4.11
17.	2-Methyl-4-nitrophenyl	4.18	0.371	401.2	49.9	4.18	4.10
18.	4-Nitrophenyl (D)	4.51	0.751	345.6	45.3	3.88	3.83
19.	2,6-Dimethyl 4-nitrophenyl	3.43	0.345	357.6	54.6	3.88	3.94
Diaryl sulphoxides							
20.	Diphenyl	3.92	0.287	388.8	59.6	4.05	—
21.	<i>p</i> -Methyldiphenyl	4.01	0.277	424.7	64.0	4.24	—
22.	<i>p</i> -Methoxydiphenyl	4.11	0.313	462.8	66.0	4.44	—
23.	Di- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl	4.04	0.326	513.8	72.2	4.69	—
24.	<i>p</i> -Nitrodiphenyl	3.19	0.376	389.0	65.1	4.01	—

*In dioxane. **For compds. sl. nos. 3, 4, 6, 7, 12, 13 and 18 calculated for free rotation, and for sl. nos. 2, 5, 9, 14, 15, 16, 17 and 19 calculated for specific conformations.

sulphonyl group in methyl *p*-methoxyphenyl sulphone shows weak conjugation with the methoxy group as judged by the dipole moment (5.27D)²³ of the sulphone ; the moment calculated from group moments is 5.00D²⁴. The observed dipole moment of methyl *p*-aminophenyl sulphone (6.42D)²⁵ as compared to its calculated moment (5.56D)²⁴, shows a much greater interaction of the *para*-substituents, the amino group being a more powerful electron-donor than methoxyl. It would indeed be of interest to know the dipole moments of methyl *p*-aminophenyl and methyl *p*-dimethylaminophenyl sulphoxides but our attempts to prepare them in pure form were not successful.

The dipole moment of methyl 4-methoxy-2,5-dimethylphenyl sulphoxide (5.10D) is in good agreement with the value (5.14D) calculated for conformation 3, indicating that the methoxy and methylsulphinyl groups assume *trans*-orientation with respect to the *o*-methyl groups. In methyl 4-methoxy-3-methylphenyl sulphoxide also the methoxy group has a similar conformation.

In the case of methyl 4-methoxy-2,6-dimethylphenyl sulphoxide the moment calculated for the conformation, in which the plane of the moment of the SOMe group and the plane of the benzene ring are mutually perpendicular, agrees well with the experimental value. The dipole moment of methyl 2,6-dimethylphenyl sulphoxide, calculated for similar conformation of the SOMe group, is in excellent agreement with the observed moment.

Methyl 4-nitrophenyl sulphoxide does not indicate any significant conjugative interaction between the nitro and methylsulphinyl groups. This is in contrast with what is observed in the case of methyl *p*-nitrophenyl sulphide¹¹ for which the observed dipole moment (4.43D) is considerably higher than the calculated one (3.90D). The methylsulphinyl group is thus a very weak electron-donor even when a powerful electron-withdrawing group like NO₂ is present in the *para*-position. This situation is in the ground state of the molecule. In the excited state the electron-releasing power of the group is higher as judged from the uv spectrum of the compound⁶.

The behaviour of methyl 2-methyl-4-nitrophenyl sulphoxide is not very much different from that of methyl 4-nitrophenyl sulphoxide. The dipole

moment of methyl 2,6-dimethyl-4-nitrophenyl sulphoxide, calculated for conformation of the SOMe group similar to that in other 2,6-dimethyl sulphoxides (sl. nos. 5 and 16 of Table 2), agrees well with the experimental moment.

References

1. H. GOETZ, B. KLABUHN, F. MARSCNER, H. HOHBERG and W. SKUBALLA, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, 27, 999.
2. W. A. SHEPPARD and R. W. TAFT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 1919.
3. F. G. BORDWELL and P. J. BOUTAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 717.
4. N. C. CUTRESS, T. B. GRINDLEY, A. R. KATRITZSKY, M. SHOME and R. D. TOPSOM, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1974, 263.
5. G. B. BUCHANAN, C. REYES-ZAMORA and D. E. CLARKE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1974, 52, 3895.
6. V. BALIAH and R. VARADACHARI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, 28, 116.
7. V. BALIAH and K. GANAPATHY, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, 59, 1784.
8. C. W. N. CUMPER and S. WALKER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, 52, 193.
9. A. I. VOGEL, W. T. CRESSWELL, G. H. JEFFREY and J. LEICESTER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 514.
10. L. G. GROVES and S. SUGDEN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1992.
11. V. BALIAH and M. UMA, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 455.
12. E. H. HUNTRESS and F. H. CARTEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 511.
13. C. E. COLBY and C. S. MCLOUGHLIN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1887, 20, 198.
14. G. LEANDRI, A. MANGINI and R. PASSERINI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1386.
15. H. H. SZMANT and J. J. MCINTOSH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4356.
16. V. BALIAH and R. VARADACHARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 37, 321.
17. H. RHEINBOLDT and E. GIESBRECHT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 973.
18. C. C. PRICE and J. J. HYDOCK, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1943.
19. Th. ZINCKE and P. JORG, *Chem. Ber.*, 1910, 43, 3448, 3450.
20. O. FUCHS, *Z. Phys. Chem (B)*, 1931, 14, 339.
21. C. G. LE FLÈVRE, R. J. W. LE FLÈVRE and K. W. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 480.
22. C. W. N. CUMPER, A. I. VOGEL and S. WALKER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 3640.
23. M. T. ROGERS, G. M. BARROW and F. G. BORDWELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 1790.
24. V. BALIAH, Unpublished observation.
25. H. LUMBROSO and R. PASSERINI, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Ft.*, 1955, 22, 1179.